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OSMOSIS

KD 4.1: Manufacture and test honeycomb Panels

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CUSTOMER: Public
Project Number 757088

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 757088

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List of Acronyms/abbreviations

ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
CAA	Chromic Acid Anodised
EDX	Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
ESA	European Space Agency
FBE	Fusion bonded epoxy
LHS	Left Hand Side
PAA	Phosphoric Acid Anodised
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals.
RHS	Right Hand Side
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TDS	Technical Data Sheet

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Reference Documents

Document No.	Document Reference	Description
[1]	ENB.PRD.B11	Sample Metallurgical Preparation System
[2]	ENB.PRD.B12	Tensile Tester Operation
[3]	ASTM D 1781 – 98(2012)	Standard Test Method for Climbing Drum Peel for Adhesives
[4]	OSMOSIS KD 2.1 Report	Comparison Between SoA and CoBlast Treatments
[5]	[link]	TDS for Redux 312 adhesive
[6]	[link]	TDS for Honeycomb Core
[7]	[link]	Webpage for Honeycomb Material
[8]	[link]	Redux Adhesive Bonding Handbook

OPEN DATA REQUIREMENT

ENBIO have shared the data associated with this Key Deliverable through ResearchGate. The OSMOSIS Project link is:

<https://www.researchgate.net/project/OSMOSIS-One-Step-Modification-Of-Space-Integrated-Surfaces>

Public data is also being made available on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/osmosis/>

Updates relating to this Key Deliverable and dataset will also be made on the ENBIO website.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Honeycomb panels consist of faceplates bonded to a lightweight core material. They exhibit extremely high strength/weight ratio. For this reason, they are commonly used in construction of spacecraft, aircraft and high-performance automotive applications.

Figure 1 Exploded view of typical aluminium honeycomb panel construction.

Picture credit: plasticore.com [\[link\]](#)

This construction relies on an adhesive to securely fasten the core and faceplate material. In the case of metal components, this often requires surface preparation of the metal faces prior to bonding. Current state-of-the-art adhesive surface preparations rely on wet chemical chromate anodisation steps to ensure a suitable bondable surface. An additional adhesive primer finish is also frequently necessary as this anodised layer only retains good adhesive properties for a 4-6 hour period following deposition¹. The use of an adhesive primer can extend this window up to months.

In order to evaluate the suitability of the CoBlast process as an alternative adhesive primer for honeycomb panels, various combinations of untreated and CoBlasted panels were produced. Identical panels featuring a current state-of-the-art surface preparation were also sourced as comparisons. Additionally, various methods of treating the core material were investigated.

Samples were constructed using various combinations of the above panels and cores and tested to ASTM D 1781 – 98(2012) Standard Test Method for Climbing Drum Peel for Adhesives.

¹ Redux Bonding Technology Handbook- Page 9 [8]

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2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Base materials

In all cases the component materials of the panels were identical:

Faceplates: 0.5 mm Aluminium 2024 T3 supplied by Amari Ireland Ltd. as 300 x 250 mm plates (with grain flow along 300 mm direction).

Adhesive: Hexcel Redux 312L 150g/m² supplied by AIM Altitude (Cambridge, UK) [5]

Core: 3.2mm Aluminium 5052 Honeycomb **15mm** from Easycomposites (UK) 2500mm x 1250mm [6][7].

Table 1 Core properties

Alloy	Cell Size		Density		Foil Thickness	Perforated	Corrosion Treated
	Units	mm	inches	lb/ft ³	kg/m ³		
5052	3.2	1/8	4.5	76.9	35	No*	No**

2.2 Surface treatments

A range of surface treatments were applied to both the honeycomb core and faceplate materials-

CoBlast

CoBlast adhesive primer formulation consists of a fusion bonded epoxy (FBE) powder, deposited in conjunction with a metal oxide corrosion inhibiting pigment. An alumina abrasive is included during blasting however its inclusion in the final coating is minimal. Details of the CoBlast process are not included here as it is covered in detail elsewhere. Further details on product development can be found in OSMOSIS KD2.1 Report [4].

Chromic Acid Anodisation (CAA)

Commercial metal finisher process, completed by AMFNI, Ballymena NI.

Degreased	Using Turco 6849
Alkaline Clean	(Turco 4215) 55-60°C. Completely immersed for 10-15 minutes
Post Alkaline Rinsing	Total immersion- rinse time between 5-15 minutes.
Acid Cleaning and De-Oxidizing	Immerse parts completely in the tri-acid etch tank 2-3 mins
Chromic Acid Anodising-	solution temperature of 32-38°C.
	40/50-volt process: anodise for 40 minutes minimum
Rinsing Post Anodising	3-5 minutes.

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Adhesive primer

State of the art anodised parts require bonding or further treatment within a 4-6-hour window as outside of this timeframe bond strength start to deteriorate. As per the adhesive manufacturer's recommendation, Redux 112 bond primer was applied to the Chromic Acid Anodised parts following treatment.

Ongoing trials indicate CoBlast-deposited materials remain stable in ambient conditions for several months with no additional treatment or primer required.

2.3 Treated components

2.3.1 Faceplates

- Bare: as supplied
- CAA with Redux 112 Primer. Bare faceplates were delivered to a commercial metal finisher and CAA treated as per process above. A Redux 112 bond primer was applied.
- CoBlast: Treated with proprietary CoBlast adhesive primer formulation consisting of FBE and metal oxide.

2.3.2 Core

A comparison was also made between untreated and treated core. For treated core this was further divided into treatment of expanded and unexpanded core material. Core material is supplied unexpanded, with layers of foil sitting stacked one on top of another. This is sometimes referred to as HOBE- Honeycomb Before Expansion. Only when expanded by uniformly extending does this material takes on the final honeycomb structure used in panel constructions.

It was decided to investigate the effect of coating this unexpanded core material in addition to expanded. Blasting the unexpanded core was expected to give a coating on only the material face- that closest to the face plate material. Blasting the expanded material would give a coating which extended partway into the honeycomb structure. This was seen as beneficial as adhesive was known to "fillet", clinging partially to the sides of the core material.

Figure 2 Honeycomb structure detail [credit: ESA [Honeycomb Study](#) undertaken by Riga University]

Initial trials used a core material fully expanded to its final, bondable form. It was noted that much primer material went to waste however as it simply passed through the open cell structure. Instead, the core material was blasted in a partially expanded state before being fully expanded to the final, bondable form. The high-pressure air jet used in the CoBlast process also served to expand the area of material undergoing blasting- resulting in better separation of adjacent layers in that area.

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The setup for partially expanded core consisted of two metal rods with a number of zip ties joining the rods to the core edges. Although crude, this approach was found to work well and is quite similar to techniques observed commercially. When separated, this applied a force to expand the core material, while the ability of the ties to slide along the rods allowed for the corresponding contraction of the core in that direction. This contraction also needed to be taken into account when sectioning the core material to ensure the final form would be the correct size.

Thus, three core variants were investigated-

- Bare: untreated, as supplied
- Unexpanded CoBlasted-Core: blasted in its unexpanded state before being expanded to its final useable form
- Expanded CoBlasted-Core: material which was partially expanded, CoBlasted and then fully expanded to its final useable form.

Figure 3 Fully expanded core prior to blasting (blasted in 2 angled passes on each side to ensure coverage of side walls. 60 degree angle.) 4 passes total- noted to be very wasteful and ultimately abandoned in favour of partially expanded.

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Figure 4 Fully expanded core post blast

Figure 5 Partially expanded core prior to blasting

Figure 6 Unexpanded core post-blast detail. Note: edge regions were partially expanded by air stream.

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2.4 Summary

In total, 7 combinations of the above core and plate materials were produced, as per Table 2 below. This allowed for a direct comparison of CoBlast vs CAA vs. bare face material as well as Bare, CoBlast Unexpanded and CoBlast Expanded core material.

From each of these panels, a total of three testable samples (per ASTM D 1781 [3]) could be extracted. Extra samples were included to account for scrap parts and customer demonstrator parts.

Table 2 Breakdown of samples constructed

Core	Plate	Total Panels (samples)	Test Panels (samples)	Spare Panels (samples)
Bare	Bare	3 (9)	2 (6)	1 (3)
	SoA	3 (9)	2 (6)	1 (3)
	CoBlast	4 (12)	2 (6)	2 (6)
CoBlast Expanded	CoBlast	4 (12)	2 (6)	2 (6)
	SoA	4 (12)	2 (6)	2 (6)
CoBlast Unexpanded	CoBlast	4 (12)	2 (6)	2 (6)
	SoA	4 (12)	2 (6)	2 (6)

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2.5 Layup and Bonding

All materials were supplied coated and ready for bonding to Kemfast Pass (Belfast, NI) who specialise in aerospace supply, manufacture and testing. They undertook all layup and bonding activities.

250 x 300 mm panels were constructed in an autoclave, vacuum bag setup. Three 76.2 x 304.8 mm (3" x 12") samples were then extracted from each of these panels, per ASTM D 1781. Extracted samples were returned to ENBIO for testing.

Additional panels were included to account for scrap parts and customer samples. Scrap rates were low, with the exception of bare-bare configuration.

Figure 7 Set of 3 extracted samples, as supplied by Kemfast Pass.

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Figure 8 Extracted samples labelled as customer samples

Testing was carried out to ASTM D 1781 [3] using a climbing drum peel test apparatus obtained through www.grip.de used in conjunction with a Mecmesin i10 tensile tester.

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Figure 9 Picture of Climbing Drum fixture setup at ENBIO.

Sandwich Peel Test

Fig. 1 Specimen Configuration

Fig. 2 Climbing drum apparatus

Figure 10 From Redux bonding handbook- p22 [8]

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Displacement/force curves were recorded for each sample as well as for bare, unbonded faceplates; i.e. a strip of aluminium of 0.5mm and width 76mm was rolled.

From ASTM D 1781:

“Measuring the force of rolling this unbonded face serves to approximate the torque required to both roll the drum upward and to bend the adherend material. By subtraction of this value, F_0 , an approximation of the peel force (only) of the adhesive can be made. However, it is noted in the standard (and confirmed by observation of the level of deformation of these faceplate material after each test): “The forces imposed on the adherend during the peel test usually result in greater bending than is obtained in bending the unbonded adherend around the drum. More torque is required, therefore, to bend a bonded than an unbonded material; hence, this compensation is only approximate.”

A test program was devised using the Mecmesin Emperor software as follows:

Clamp sample appropriately and raise until drum assembly is suspended

Run programme “honeycomb template”:

- zero force measurement.
- Run at 250 mm/min until an additional force was detected (this is the reason that force curves below begin at $\approx 50\text{N}$ as opposed to at the origin. This should not interfere with results however as the standard calls for first 25mm of peel data to be discarded).
- Displacement value zeroed, test then run at standard-recommended crosshead speed of 25 mm/s.
- Force/Displacement curve recorded over full length of specimen.
- Test stopped manually before climbing drum crashed into upper clamp.

The standard specifies to discard first 25 mm of peel data (1 inch), which corresponds to 6.4 mm of crosshead travel. However, crosshead travel in this case was recorded from first detectable force as opposed to first peel force. So instead, a value of 15mm crosshead displacement was used as a cut off- this ensured the values were recorded from 6.35 mm or more within the peel zone of the plot.

Additionally, the standard calls for the average force to be calculated over 127mm (5”) of peeled area, corresponding to 38.1mm crosshead displacement. Thus, values after 48mm were also omitted when calculating average peel forces.

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Figure 11 Relationship between sample size, crosshead travel and Force-Displacement curves

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Cutoff material from each combination of surfaces was mounted in epoxy, ground, polished to sub-micron roughness and imaged using Phenom XL SEM.

Figure 12 Honeycomb sections mounted in epoxy and polished in preparation for viewing under SEM [1]

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3 RESULTS

3.1 Overall Peel Results and Discussion

As per the standard, a minimum of 6 samples were run for each combination of materials. Force-Displacement graphs for each are given below (Figures 17 - 23). In some cases, it was necessary to include results from peeling the reverse side of some panels also. These results have a “B” suffix below (for “back”). All other results have an “F” suffix for “front”. Some additional deformation was noted in samples which were peeled on both sides, however overall the samples remained rigid and the front and back results were in good agreement.

Figure 13 Extracted sample following peel testing

As discussed, the first 10mm of data was discarded and an average calculated over 127mm of each sample. These results are given in Tables 5-12 below each respective Figure. These averages are calculated from all data points between 10 – 48 mm of crosshead travel.

Table 3 Overall Average Peel Force Results

Face Material	Core Material	Overall average (N)	St Dev	% St dev	# samples
Bare	n/a	189.61	5.38	2.84	7
Bare	Bare	200.28	5.77	2.88	1
CoBlast	Bare	663.82	67.62	10.19	6
CAA	Bare	634.70	59.88	9.43	6
CoBlast	CoBlast E	562.19	45.91	8.17	7
CAA	CoBlast E	566.97	54.06	9.53	6
CoBlast	CoBlast U	542.00	45.92	8.47	6
CAA	CoBlast U	494.89	37.67	7.61	6

Figure 14 Overall results expressed in bar graph form

Observations

- Bare-bare peel force was measured just higher than the value of rolling a face only sample, indicating a very weak bond. These bonds could be separated by hand and often failed before they could be tested- only one sample was successfully run to completion.
- Bare core performed better than CoBlast Expanded or CoBlast Unexpanded core (Figure 15).
- CoBlast faceplates performed as well or better than SoA CAA faceplates.

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- Two distinct force patterns were observed:
 - low force, oscillating with high frequency
 - higher average force, oscillating with lower frequency

It is assumed these modes correspond to core alignment. In one direction (W axis in Figure 16 below), a “barrier” of aligned bonded corners must be overcome (high force). Once overcome, a large drop is observed until the next barrier is reached. This results in a sawtooth waveform of high amplitude. Along the L axis, the corner regions are better distributed and thus lower overall force. Ideally, all core alignments should have been uniform however as supplied they were in various orientations across all samples.

Figure 15 From mil standard MIL-STD-401B

3.2 Individual Honeycomb Peel Results

3.2.1 Bare Face Bare Core & Unbonded Face Only

Figure 16 Bare face bare core & faceplate only results.

*As these results were recorded from a Force of 0 N (instead of the 30-70N values used below), averages were calculated from 35mm crosshead displacement and above.

Table 4 Results table for Unbonded Face Only samples

Sample #	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Overall
Average	190.58	188.12	187.61	187.20	195.22	189.11	189.40	189.61
St.Dev	6.08	4.66	4.57	4.55	4.76	5.18	7.84	5.38

Table 5 Bare Face Bare Core Results Table

Sample #	1
Average	203.33
St.Dev	7.83

3.2.2 CoBlast Face Bare Core

Figure 17 CoBlast Face Bare Core

Table 6 Results Table

	1F	1B	3F	3B	4F	5F	Overall average
Average	627.42	721.33	642.47	649.40	617.17	725.11	663.82
St.Dev	61.61	69.79	62.39	57.69	89.16	65.08	67.62

3.2.3 CAA Face Bare Core

Figure 18 CAA Face Bare Core

Table 7 Results table

	1F	1B	3F	3B	4F	4B	Overall average
Average	622.13	624.31	619.68	654.15	627.82	660.11	634.70
St.Dev	52.32	55.80	65.43	60.20	64.17	61.36	59.88

3.2.4 CoBlast Face CoBlast Expanded Core

Figure 19 CoBlast Face CoBlast Expanded Core

Table 8 Results table

	1F	2F	3F	4F	6F	7F	8F	Overall Average
Average	477.63	563.35	502.90	581.83	595.91	502.28	603.82	562.19
St.Dev	28.89	47.95	34.69	50.77	49.82	26.57	45.26	45.91

3.2.5 CAA Face CoBlast Expanded Core

Figure 20 CAA Face CoBlast Expanded Core

Table 9 Results table

	1F	2F	3F	4F	5F	6F	Overall average
Average	657.88	505.71	531.97	632.15	555.00	519.10	566.97
St.Dev	54.54	40.79	50.35	49.91	56.74	72.02	54.06

3.2.6 CoBlast Face CoBlast Unexpanded Core

Figure 21 CoBlast face CoBlast Unexpanded Core

Table 10 Results table

	1F	1B	3F	3B	4F	4B	Overall average
Average	692.77	553.32	414.28	420.99	518.36	652.27	542.00
St.Dev	53.45	46.70	36.19	35.36	41.11	62.68	45.92

3.2.7 CAA Face CoBlast Unexpanded Core

Figure 22 CAA Face CoBlast Unexpanded Core

Table 11 Results Table

	1F	2F	3F	4F	5F	6F	Overall average
Average	434.68	566.99	559.73	508.96	453.70	445.31	494.89
St.Dev	37.66	57.25	43.05	35.85	22.91	29.33	37.67

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3.3 Cross section Results and Discussion

Figure 23 CAA face, CoBlast Unexpanded core

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Carbon

Aluminium

Oxygen

Copper

Magnesium

Chloride

Chromium

Titanium

Observations and discussion-

- Core foil thickness ~30 μm
- CAA layer observable, thickness approx. 2 μm . Uniform coverage, even in areas with imperfections.
- Aluminium alloys discernible- core 5000 series (Al + Mg), face 2000 series (Al + Cu + Mg)
- “shoe” feature- observed in base of many core sections. Presumably an artefact of the core cutting process- a saw burr. Material partially drawn out in direction of saw blade.
- CoBlast coating discernible by metal oxide pigment- only face and a small area of the core coated, as evidenced by Ti Map.

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Figure 24 Cross section showing region of 2 core foils meeting and adhesive fillet. Metal shavings from extraction process indicate adhesive and mounting epoxy interface.

- Fillet of adhesive observable. Interface of mounting epoxy and adhesive just about discernible, aided by metal shavings from extraction process. Shows a large fillet on LHS extending $\sim 400\mu\text{m}$ and smaller on RHS extending $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$. Likely this is a result of vacuum bag forming process- additional material was drawn to the vacuum side as air pressure in LHS cell dropped and adhesive became less viscous. A perforated core, available for space or vacuum applications would mitigate this effect.

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Figure 25 CoBlast face, CoBlast Expanded core. Higher magnification of above with EDX maps below.

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Table 12 Elemental Maps

- Region where two core foils are converging or diverging.
- CoBlast Expanded core- sides coated as evidenced by Ti map. Contrast to CoBlast Unexpanded core above, where only bottom face was covered. Area between faces not coated- likely region of core adhesive.
- Roughened surface of CoBlast process visible on all faces.

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4 CONCLUSIONS

CoBlasted core was found not to perform as well as the untreated equivalent. The reason for this has not been identified- possibly due to micro deformation of the surface resulting in less intimate contact with the faceplates.

The peel forces indicate that CoBlasted face performs equally as well as CAA-treated face plates. This is beneficial as it eliminates the need for harmful wet chemical processes (namely chromic acid anodising) as well as the addition of high-solvent primer. This not only reduces the number of process steps but results in an overall cleaner, more environmentally friendly process.